

The Mercury/Mercurous Acetate Electrode: Standard Potentials, and related Thermodynamic Quantities in Dioxan-Water Media at Different Temperatures

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The standard potentials have been determined for the cell

at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° over a range of dioxan-water mixtures. The related thermodynamic quantities have been evaluated. The dependence of the standard potentials on the dielectric constants of the media in the light of the Born equation as well as the volume-fraction of water (ϕ_w) in the light of Feakins-French relationship and the variation of the thermodynamic quantities with various parameters associated with solvent media have been examined.

In a previous communication¹ we reported the accurate standard potentials of the mercury/mercurous acetate electrode in Dioxan-water media at 25°. In this one we report the determination of the temperature coefficient of standard potentials of this electrode, in the same medium and evolution of related thermodynamic quantities such as the standard free energies, enthalpies and entropies of the cell reaction. For the purpose, the e.m.f.'s of the cell,

were determined at 15°, 20°, 25°, 30° and 35°.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials, preparation of electrodes, accuracy of analysis and technique of the measurements, were described in our previous communication¹. The cell e.m.f.'s were measured first from 25° to 35° and then from 15° to 25°. The e.m.f. values at 25° at the first and at the last were in excellent agreement i.e., within 0.10 mV. The temperature control of the air thermostat was within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. All the electromotive force readings were corrected to one atmosphere pressure of hydrogen. The solvent compositions were 20, 30, 45 and 70 percent of dioxan in water. In 70% by weight of Dioxan-Water system acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer was used. For all other solvent compositions only acetic acid was used. The values of dielectric constant, density and vapour pressure of solvents, ionisation constant of acetic acid etc., at the above-mentioned temperature were taken from the works as mentioned in our previous communication¹.

1. A. K. Basu and S. Aditya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48,

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The measured electromotive forces (in abs. V.) of the cell corrected to one atmosphere pressure of hydrogen are listed in Table I with their respective molal concentrations of acetic acid (m_1) and sodium acetate (m_2).

TABLE I

Molality		Electromotives Forces of the Cell in abs. V.				
m_1	m_2	15°C	20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C
20% Dioxan by weight						
1.7986	—	0.78067	0.78218	0.78398	0.78289	0.78693
1.6154	—	0.78222	0.78423	0.78563	0.78579	0.78908
1.5486	—	0.78167	0.78368	0.78578	0.78769	0.78998
1.4030	—	0.78332	0.78518	0.78693	0.78889	0.79078
1.2625	—	0.78572	0.78733	0.78943	0.79159	0.79353
1.1394	—	0.79007	0.79203	0.79283	0.79439	0.79793
0.99212	—	0.79297	0.79518	0.79738	0.79759	0.80198
0.84970	—	0.79687	0.79893	0.80108	0.80179	0.80543
0.70946	—	0.80057	0.80298	0.80518	0.80654	0.81008
0.56755	—	0.80517	0.80783	0.81018	0.81264	0.81523
30% Dioxan by weight						
1.9036	—	0.77977	0.78196	0.78428	0.78674	0.78943
1.7201	—	0.78317	0.78521	0.78713	0.78934	0.79153
1.5072	—	0.78587	0.78796	0.79008	0.79204	0.79418
1.2929	—	0.78927	0.79156	0.79368	0.79589	0.79813
1.0790	—	0.79352	0.79536	0.79738	0.79934	0.80148
0.96720	—	0.79547	0.79756	0.79978	0.80214	0.80428
0.86352	—	0.79927	0.80076	0.80288	0.80504	0.80734
0.75663	—	0.80202	0.80431	0.80663	0.80904	0.81148
0.64869	—	0.80617	0.80791	0.81023	0.81269	0.81528
0.54050	—	0.80827	0.81096	0.81353	0.81634	0.81928
45% Dioxan by weight						
1.3327	—	0.79436	0.79586	0.79754	0.79961	0.80166
1.2267	—	0.79531	0.79681	0.79924	0.80176	0.80431
1.1207	—	0.79686	0.79916	0.80149	0.80371	0.80586
1.0149	—	0.79966	0.80096	0.80289	0.80521	0.80756
0.98799	—	0.80116	0.80286	0.80484	0.80716	0.80951
0.91067	—	0.80261	0.80436	0.80659	0.80901	0.81156
0.82627	—	0.80476	0.80691	0.80934	0.81196	0.81461
0.74226	—	0.80751	0.80971	0.81189	0.81431	0.81686
0.65637	—	0.81081	0.81316	0.81539	0.81781	0.82026
0.57308	—	0.81416	0.81626	0.81854	0.82101	0.82356
70% Dioxan by weight						
0.64731	0.03222	0.82098	0.82279	0.82483	0.82703	0.82942
0.66312	0.02766	0.82953	0.82139	0.82303	0.82503	0.82702
0.67512	0.02421	0.81863	0.81989	0.82198	0.82428	0.82672
0.66792	0.02628	0.81973	0.82104	0.82303	0.82508	0.82742
0.66858	0.02213	0.81783	0.81929	0.82133	0.82348	0.82542
0.68708	0.02015	0.81733	0.81899	0.82058	0.82268	0.82492
0.69182	0.01938	0.81723	0.81874	0.82098	0.82338	0.82587
0.69661	0.01799	0.81618	0.81729	0.81943	0.82288	0.82392
0.70141	0.01661	0.81763	0.81899	0.82048	0.82188	0.82342
0.71099	0.01384	0.81523	0.81674	0.81818	0.81968	0.82242

The cell reaction for the above-mentioned cell is

The standard potentials of the mercury/mercurous acetate electrodes were calculated from the equation (except for 70% w/w Dioxan-water media).

$$E = E_m^0 - 2k \log m_1 \alpha \gamma \quad \dots (1)$$

where $k = 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F}$

The degree of dissociation (α) and mean ionic activity coefficients (γ_{\pm}) have been calculated by successive approximation from the dissociation constant expression

$$K = \frac{m_1^2 \alpha^2 \gamma_{\pm}^2}{m_1(1-\alpha)\gamma_u} \quad \dots (2)$$

and the Debye-Huckel equation

$$\log \gamma_{\pm} = - \frac{Az_+z_-\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + Ba\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where γ_u is the activity coefficient of unionised acetic acid molecules and considered as unity for our calculation. All other symbols have their usual significance and calculated in the usual way.

As mentioned earlier¹ the E_m^0 values determined from equation (1) using equations (2) and (3) were not constant and have been designated as $E^{0'}_m$. The plot of $E^{0'}_m$ against μ extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave the correct standard potential of the electrode in that media.

For 70% dioxan-water media the e.m.f. relation is

$$E^{0'} = E_m^0 - k.S.\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

where S is known as salting coefficient and

$$E^{0'} = E + k \log K + k \log (m_1 - m')$$

$$m' = K \frac{m_1}{m_2}$$

and E_m^0 was obtained by the extrapolation of the linear plot of $E^{0'}$ against μ .

The standard free energy change (ΔG^0) for the cell reaction at the different temperatures in dioxan-water media have been calculated from the thermodynamic relation,

$$\Delta G^0 = -nFE^0 \quad \dots (5)$$

where n is the number of electrons transferred in the reaction and ' F ' is the Faraday and its value taken as 23.062 Cal. abs. v^{-1} mole $^{-1}$.

The enthalpies (ΔH^0) were evaluated from the relation,

$$\Delta H^0 = \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\Delta G^0}{T} \right)}{\partial \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)} \quad \dots (6)$$

by plotting $\Delta G^0/T$ against $1/T$ and taking the slope of the curve.

The entropies (ΔS^0) were obtained from

$$\Delta S^0 = \frac{\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0}{T} \quad \dots (7)$$

The standard potentials of the electrode and the calculated thermodynamic quantities are given in Table II. All these values in water medium were taken from the work of Larson².

TABLE II

Values of Derived Quantities in Dioxan-water Media at Different Temperatures

Solvent (by wt. percent)	Temp. °C	E_m^0 abs. V.	ΔG^0 Kcal	ΔH^0 Kcal	ΔS^0 , E.U. (cal.deg. ⁻¹)
20% Dioxan	15	0.48520	-22.380		
	20	0.48260	-22.260		
	25	0.48035	-22.156	-29.03	-23.0
	30	0.47770	-22.034		
	35	0.47515	-21.916		
30% Dioxan	15	0.46660	-21.522		
	20	0.46300	-21.356		
	25	0.45980	-21.208	-30.34	-30.6
	30	0.45680	-21.070		
	35	0.45390	-20.936		
45% Dioxan	15	0.43965	-20.278		
	20	0.43580	-20.100		
	25	0.43170	-19.912	-31.30	-38.2
	30	0.42740	-19.714		
	35	0.42290	-19.506		
70% Dioxan	15	0.32880	-15.166		
	20	0.32170	-14.838		
	25	0.31400	-14.482	-34.44	-37.0
	30	0.30695	-14.158		
	35	0.30000	-13.838		

DISCUSSION

The values of E_m^0 at 15°, 20°, 25°, 30° and 35° were plotted against solvent composition in weight percent of dioxan. In media with lower percentage of dioxan the plots are almost linear, the deviation increases with increase in dioxan in the media. This departure from linearity increases with the increase of temperature. The plots of E_m^0 values against T for all solvent compositions are linear over the range. The temperature coefficient of E_m^0 values, however, increases with the increase of dioxan in the solvent.

For each temperature values of E_m^0 were plotted against $1/D$ (Born plot), $\log \phi_w$ (Feakins and French plot) and mole fraction of dioxan. As observed in our previous work¹ the Feakins and French plot showed better linearity than Born plot. The values of E_m^0 against mole fraction plot showed a still better linearity.

The plots of free energies, enthalpies and entropies of the cell reaction against weight percent of dioxan, $1/D$, $\log \phi_w$ and mole fraction of dioxan are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3

Fig. 1. Plot of ΔG^0 against $1/D$, $\log \phi_w$, wt. % and molefraction of Dioxan at 25°C.

respectively. The variation of ΔG^0 against $\log \phi_w$ and mole fraction of dioxan are linear. The enthalpies (ΔH^0) and entropies (ΔS^0) pass through a maximum (nearly at 20% dioxan media) in all types of plots. This type of behaviour, i.e., passing through a maximum of

Fig. 2. Plot of ΔH^0 Against $1/D$, $\log \phi_w$, wt. % and molefraction of Dioxan at 25°C

the enthalpies and entropies were also seen by McIntyre and Amis³ for the cell reaction of the Pt, H₂/HI(m)/AgI-Ag and Pt, H₂/HCl(m)/AgCl-Ag cells in methanol-water media. The thermodynamic quantities for acetic acid in water and dioxan-water media from the

Fig. 3. Plot of ΔS° , e.u. against $1/D$, $\log \phi_w$, wt. % and molefraction of Dioxan at 25°C.

work of Harned and co-workers⁴ were plotted against solvent compositions. ΔH^0 values pass-through a maximum. The entropy values apparently do not show a definite maximum trend, yet the data indicate a trend that the ΔS^0 may have a maximum lying around 15% W/W dioxan in dioxan-water media. Although the variation of the thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0) with the composition of media in the present work is similar to the observation made by other workers³⁻⁴, with the present state of our knowledge (with so little experimental work available) it is not possible to speculate any physical explanation for this.

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